

NUTRI•KNOW

STRUVITE (IT)

RENURE (BE)

GAS LOOP (IT)

POCKETBOER 2 (BE)

SOS_AQUAE (IT)

Grass2Algae (BE)

FERTICOOP-GO (ES)

MOPS (IE)

Manure Management Tool (ES)

Duncannon Blue Flag Farming (IE)

Slurry Concentrator (ES)

Biorefinery Glas (IE)

Exchanging easy-to-understand nutrient management knowledge with farmers

NUTRI-KNOW aims to improve nutrient management practices in agriculture by establishing an ongoing cycle of knowledge exchange for the benefit of both farmers and the environment.

FERTICOOP

Innovations to adapt to the best available techniques (BAT) in the Catalan cooperative agricultural sector

Develop innovation tools for a better management of manure and agricultural fertilisations, achieving a valorisation of slurry and improvement in the quality of the extensive crops that are produced.

Goal

Evaluation of BAT in different farms to identify the chemical fertility of soils and to reduce the amount of phosphorus in soils.

Activity

- Testing different methodologies and tools to evaluate the chemical fertility of soils.
- Testing strategies to reduce the amount of phosphorus in soils of different characteristics (irrigated, arid and semi-arid).

Results

- Evaluation of different BATs depending on the characteristics of the different fields and training farmers on them.
- Reducing the use of mineral fertilisers.
- Evaluation of recommendations to reduce phosphorus in different soils.

Training of farmers about analysed BATs

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our journey!

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